

PREPARATION OF ORGANOSILANE TREATED MICROCRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE (SiMCC) AND THE POLYPROPYLENE/ SiMCC COMPOSITE

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Abstract

In this study, the polypropylene/ silane treated microcrystalline cellulose (SiMCC) composite was prepared. In the first step, the surface modification of microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) with various concentrations of hexadecyltrimethoxysilane was carried-out in order to obtain the SiMCC having good compatibility with PP matrix. Characterizations including SEM, FT-IR, TGA and DSC were employed to analyze the structure of SiMCC. SEM revealed that MCC surface morphology was changed from rod shape into rough particles after silane treatment. In the next step, the obtained SiMCC was mixed with PP powder using twin-screw extruder. The compatibility was achieved, as evidenced by various techniques.

Introduction

Cellulosic /polymer composites are the important branches in the field of composite materials. Compared with conventional inorganic fillers, cellulose provide many advantages such as abundance and low cost, flexibility during processing and less resulting machine wear, desirable fiber aspect ratio, low density, minimal health hazard and biodegradable.[1] One of the most used reinforcement fillers is microcrystalline cellulose (MCC). It is easy to prepare by reacting cellulose with aqueous solution of strong mineral acid at boiling temperature for a period of time. The hydrolysis reaction removes amorphous cellulose and reduces the degree of polymerization (level-off degree of polymerization, LODP) of the cellulose chain. MCC exists in rod shaped particles having a large particle size distribution. Basically, its chemical structure consists of repeating unit (anhydroglycoside unit (AGU)). Due to the high

degree of crystallinity, microcrystalline cellulose is not swollen in water, stable to temperature and pH variations when compared to cellulose.[2] Moreover, MCC is hydrophilic and tends to result in phase separation when incorporated into polymer matrix, causing poor compatibility. To solve this problem, surface modification of MCC is required.

The aim of this work was to prepare PP/SiMCC composites containing SiMCC having various silane to MCC ratios. The properties of the obtained composites were presented.

Methodology

Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) was prepared by acid hydrolysis of waste cotton fabric with hydrochloric acid. The white residue obtained was washed repeatedly with distilled water to obtain acid-free MCC. The MCC was then dried in a vacuum oven to constant weight and ground into fine powder. Then, the MCC was swollen in urea solution before coupling with hexadecyl triethoxysilane at 80 °C, 1 h. Silane to MCC mole ratios of 1: 1, 1: 2, 1: 3, and 1:4 were employed. Hydrochloric acid was used to adjust pH to 1. The silane treated microcrystalline cellulose (SiMCC) was characterized by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) in the range 450–4000 cm⁻¹. The MCC/PP composite and PP/SiMCC composites were prepared by twin screw operating at 180-210°C and 100 rpm using co-rotating mode. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to observe the morphology. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was performed to study the thermal behavior.

Result and discussion

Silane treated microcrystalline cellulose was characterized by FTIR spectroscopy as shown in

Fig.1. The sharp peaks at 2800-3000 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $-\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_3$ group that are not observed in FTIR spectrum of MCC. Therefore, these findings lead to conclude the presence of organosilane in the SiMCC. The band at 1134 cm^{-1} is assigned to the stretching of Si-O-Si bonds. The Si-O-C bond was expected to be found in the region of 1015-1095 cm^{-1} . Unfortunately, the fingerprint of this band is present in the same range of cellulose bands. The morphology of SiMCC is obviously different from those of MCC as shown in Fig.2. As seen, the modification of MCC with organosilane results in the transformation of MCC from fibrous shape into agglomerate particle with no aspect ratio. The particle sizes of MCC and SiMCC at various mole ratios was shown in table 1. Change in shape was evident in case of higher ratios of silane to MCC, indicating the completeness of MCC transformation. This is due to the fact that the urea swollen cellulose was able to completely react with organosilane, thus preventing it converting back into the original form.

Fig.1. The subtraction FTIR spectra of SiMCC

Table 1 Particle sizes of MCC and SiMCC at various Si:MCC mole ratios

Filler	Fibrous shape length (μm)	Agglomerate particle diameter (μm)
MCC	25-500	-
Si:MCC=1:1	25-125	12.5-75
Si:MCC=1:2	25-125	12.5-62.5
Si:MCC=1:3	25-125	12.5-75
Si:MCC=1:4	25-212.5	12.5-62.5

Fig.2. SEM micrograph of SiMCC at various mole ratio (A) Silane: MCC = 1:1 (B) 1:2 (C) 1:3 (D) 1:4 and (E) MCC

Fig.3. SEM micrograph of (A) PP, PP/SiMCC composites at various mole ratios of Silane : MCC (B)1:1 (C)1:2 (D)1:3 (E)1:4 and (F) PP/MCC composite

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As a result of hydrophobicity characteristic of SiMCC, this filler is more compatible with polypropylene than MCC as shown in Fig.3. As seen, the composites with SiMCC having more organosilane content exhibit the better compatibility, judged by the invisibility of phase separation between filler and matrix.

Fig.4. TGA Thermogram of PP, PP/SiMCC composites at various mole ratios of Silane : MCC (B)1:1 (C)1:2 (D)1:3 (E)1:4 and (F) PP/MCC composite

Fig.5. DTG Thermogram of PP, PP/SiMCC composites at various mole ratios of Silane : MCC (B)1:1 (C)1:2 (D)1:3 (E)1:4 and (F) PP/MCC composite

The decomposition of PP shows one degradation step with peak mass loss Td of 464 °C. PP/MCC composite and various PP/SiMCC composites decomposed in 2 steps as seen in Fig 4 and 5. The first step corresponds to the decomposition of cellulose and the second is polypropylene matrix degradation. In the first step, MCC/PP composite as well as PP/SiMCC1:1 composite started to

decompose at higher temperature than other composites. The decomposition temperature (Td) was 343 °C for PP/MCC composite, as shown in table 2. The thermal degradation behavior of cellulose is shown in Scheme 1. The first step involves formation of ‘active’ cellulose. This is believed to be associated with scission of glycosidic bonds, caused by transglycosylation. Cellulose undergoes depolymerisation but this does not involve mass loss. The second step consists of dehydration of pyranose rings, producing anhydrocellulose and resulting in mass loss. Further degradation of pyranose produces CO₂, various volatile gases and unsaturated cyclic compounds [3].

Scheme 1 the thermal degradation mechanism of cellulose

Table 2 First decomposition of PP/MCC and PP/SiMCC composites at various Si:MCC mole ratios in composites analyzed by TGA

Composite	Onset temperature (°C)	Degradation temperature, Td (°C)	% weight loss
PP/MCC	343	365	25.40
PP/Si:MCC1:1	341	370	8.00
PP/Si:MCC1:2	337	361	14.40
PP/Si:MCC1:3	337	361	16.00
PP/Si:MCC1:4	332	351	18.00

The modification of microcrystalline cellulose using high organosilane (Si:MCC1:1) can increase the degradation temperature of the composite thanks to the compatibility between Si:MCC1:1 powder and PP matrix. Both MCC and SiMCC can increase the degradation temperature of the composite as seen in the second decomposition shown in table 3. This is

due to the addition of foreign particles which favorably induce the crystallization of polypropylene matrix, leading to higher crystallinity of a polymer composite. This reason is also confirmed by DSC results. Fig.6 (a) and (b) show melting and crystallization behavior of PP and various composites. The presence of the MCC had little effect on the melting temperature of PP as seen in table 4. However, the percentages of crystallinity of PP/SiMCC composites and PP/MCC composite are higher than PP as seen in table 5. However, the introduction of MCC as well as SiMCC results in a slight increase in Tc since the average particle size of the filler is too big to induce the rate of PP crystallization.

Table 3 Second decomposition of PP, PP/MCC and PP/SiMCC composites at various Si:MCC mole ratios in composites analyzed by TGA

Composite	Onset temperature (°C)	Degradation temperature, Td (°C)	% weight loss	% Residue
PP	443.50	464	100	0
PP/MCC	453.83	479.00	73.34	1.26
PP/Si:MCC1:1	453.97	479.00	90.10	1.90
PP/Si:MCC1:2	453.87	479.00	85.42	0.17
PP/Si:MCC1:3	453.61	479.00	83.79	0.21
PP/Si:MCC1:4	454.14	479.00	81.32	0.68

Table 4 Melting temperature (Tm) and crystallization temperature of PP, PP/MCC and PP/SiMCC composites at various Si:MCC mole ratios in composites analyzed by DSC

Composite	Melting temperature (°C)	Crystallisation temperature (°C)
PP	155.57	119.27
PP/MCC	158.74	129.24
PP/Si:MCC1:1	153.86	120.73
PP/Si:MCC1:2	154.99	121.34
PP/Si:MCC1:3	156.35	122.13
PP/Si:MCC1:4	156.95	123.29

Table 5 enthalpy of fusion (ΔH_f) and percentage of crystallinity of PP, PP/MCC and PP/SiMCC composites at various Si:MCC mole ratios in composites analyzed by DSC

Composite	ΔH_f (J/g)	% Crystallinity
PP	77.8317	37.43
PP/MCC	64.0591	44.10
PP/Si:MCC1:1	64.9860	44.74
PP/Si:MCC1:2	68.0057	46.82
PP/Si:MCC1:3	67.8457	46.71
PP/Si:MCC1:4	64.8902	44.67

Fig.6. Heat capacity curves of PP, PP/MCC and PP/SiMCC composites at various Si:MCC mole ratios in composites, (a) melting endotherm and (b) crystallization exotherm.

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Conclusions

Silane treated microcrystalline cellulose (SiMCC) was successfully prepared. The higher organosilane to MCC ratio resulted in the higher SiMCC particle content with agglomerate form. The complete MCC transformation was achieved when 1:1 silane to MCC ratio was employed. As a result of hydrophobicity, SiMCC particles as filler additive were more compatible to PP matrix than original MCC made the PP/SiMCC1:1 composite increases its thermal stability. The addition of SiMCC into to PP matrix also led to an increase in the percentage of crystallinity due to the effect of the presence of SiMCC as foreign particles.

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